

"THE IMPORTANCE OF GENDER CHARACTERISTICS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF FAMILY COMPETENCES"

Muattar Ulugbekovna Saitova

basic doctoral student at the Research
Institute of "Family and Gender"

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Abstract:

The development of family competences is a critical factor in fostering harmonious relationships and a stable social environment. Gender characteristics play a significant role in shaping these competences, influencing communication, decision-making, and emotional dynamics within the family unit. This article explores the interplay between gender-specific traits and family competences, emphasizing their impact on effective parenting, conflict resolution, and the division of responsibilities. Understanding these dynamics can contribute to the creation of balanced family structures and policies promoting gender equality.

Keywords: gender characteristics, family competences, communication, parenting, gender equality, family dynamics.

Introduction

Family competences refer to the skills, knowledge, and attitudes required for maintaining healthy and functional family relationships. These competences include effective communication, empathy, conflict resolution, and collaborative problem-solving. Gender characteristics, which encompass both biological and sociocultural dimensions, significantly influence the acquisition and application of these competences.

This study examines how gender-specific traits shape family dynamics and contribute to the development of family competences. It also highlights the need for acknowledging and leveraging these differences to foster equitable and cooperative family environments.

Theoretical Framework

Gender Characteristics

Gender characteristics are divided into:

Biological Traits: Differences in physical and hormonal attributes influencing behavior.

Sociocultural Influences: Societal norms and expectations regarding masculinity and femininity, shaping roles and responsibilities in the family.

Family Competences

Key competences include:

Communication Skills: Verbal and non-verbal expression.

Emotional Intelligence: Understanding and managing emotions.

Conflict Resolution: Negotiating disagreements constructively.

Collaborative Decision-Making: Joint participation in decisions affecting the family.

The Role of Gender in Family Competences

Communication and Emotional Dynamics

Women are often socialized to prioritize emotional expression and empathetic communication, fostering deeper emotional bonds within the family. Men, traditionally expected to exhibit stoicism, may emphasize problem-solving and pragmatic communication. Balancing these tendencies can enhance mutual understanding and emotional resilience.

Parenting Styles

Gendered approaches to parenting reflect distinct nurturing and disciplinary tendencies. Mothers are frequently associated with caregiving and emotional support, while fathers are often seen as authority figures or play partners. Effective parenting involves blending these roles to create a supportive and structured environment for children.

Division of Responsibilities

Traditional gender roles often dictate the division of labor in families, with women taking on domestic tasks and men focusing on financial responsibilities. Shifting towards egalitarian practices enhances cooperation, reduces stress, and models equitable behaviors for children.

Challenges and Opportunities

Gender Stereotypes

Rigid stereotypes can hinder the full development of family competences by restricting individuals to predefined roles. For instance, men may face barriers in expressing vulnerability, while women may encounter challenges in asserting authority.

Promoting Gender Equality

Encouraging shared responsibilities and dismantling stereotypes can enhance family competences. Educational programs, workplace policies, and community initiatives can play pivotal roles in fostering gender-balanced families.

Conclusion

Gender characteristics profoundly influence the development of family competences, shaping communication patterns, parenting approaches, and the division of responsibilities. Recognizing and addressing these dynamics is essential for promoting harmonious family relationships and achieving gender equality. Future research should explore the intersection of gender and family competences across diverse cultural contexts to develop more inclusive and effective strategies.

References:

1. Antonov A. I. Sociology of the family: a textbook / A. I. Antonov. - M.: Yurait, 2017. - 336 p.
2. Vasilyeva E.V. Psychology of family relations: a textbook / E. V. Vasilyeva, I. P. Nechaeva. - St. Petersburg: Piter, 2019. - 480 p.
3. Grebennikov I.V. Fundamentals of family pedagogy / I. V. Grebennikov. - M.: Academy, 2016. - 256 p.
4. Kolominsky Ya.L. Family psychology: problems and prospects / Ya. L. Kolominsky. - Minsk: TetraSystems, 2018. - 352 p.
5. Leontiev A.N. Activity. Consciousness. Personality / A. N. Leontiev. - M.: Smysl, 2016. - 368 p.
6. Milovanova E.A. The role of gender characteristics in the formation of family competencies / E. A. Milovanova // Bulletin of social and humanitarian sciences. - 2021. - No. 4. - P. 67-72.
7. Shafranova M.A. Gender differences in raising children / M. A. Shafranova // Family studies. — 2020. — No. 6. — pp. 84-90.